

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF MARKETING OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES

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Abstract. *This scientific article describes the role of marketing in the higher education system, defining the main tasks of the marketing of educational services in increasing the competitiveness of higher education and ways of their implementation. In addition, suggestions and recommendations were developed for identifying and evaluating the specific aspects of educational services in the activities of higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *higher education, marketing, marketing service, higher education competitiveness, marketing activities, quality of education, personnel training, marketing of educational services.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions, the socio-economic status of the country directly depends on its contribution to the development of human civilization, science, culture and education. In this process, higher education occupies a special place as one of the main, leading factors of social, economic and cultural processes of society.

Over the past 10 years, the situation with the use of marketing in various fields of activity has changed so much that it is difficult to imagine how the HEI can manage without marketing in its programs.

But what do HEIs understand by higher education marketing? They often refer to very limited activities aimed at attracting students and developing an attractive university website. Even in the USA, the birthplace of marketing, many universities are limited to this, as evidenced by the topics covered by the American Marketing Association's 12 annual higher education marketing symposia.

For the practical use of marketing in HEI activities, it is necessary to rely on well-developed basic concepts. Therefore, it is interesting to analyze the main concepts of marketing in higher education, the trends that have already appeared in this field in Uzbekistan and the world as a whole, and the prospects for the development of this direction of marketing in the near future.

In the last decade of the 20th century, the main achievements in higher education marketing include the definition of the university product, its consumers, buyers and target audiences, as well as the realization of the need for a strategic approach to marketing activities and their organizational design.

In the conditions of limited budget funds, the commercial activity of universities gives them additional development potential. Today, almost all educational institutions provide paid educational services.

In most commercial matters, universities have sufficient independence, although some aspects of their economic and marketing activities are regulated by the state.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Scientists such as K.M.Almakuchukov [4], G. Akhunova [5], D. Nazarova [6], D. Nabiev [7], A.O. Ochilov [8,9] were involved in the issues of marketing management and its improvement

and significant results were achieved in the course of research, but the issues of managing marketing activities in the higher education system were not fully studied.

For example, G.N. Akhunova studied the analysis of marketing in the higher education system to concentrate the forces of marketers in the republican center for the provision of marketing services and to introduce ways to meet the need for specialists in the necessary educational areas (specializations) and justified the expediency of assigning functions on the basis of payment, determining, taking into account future opportunities, studying the state of the educational services market, training personnel and other issues.

During the development of marketing activity, the definitions given to it are being updated. Nowadays, there is an increasing need to apply marketing strategy not only for studying and developing enterprise activities, but also in social spheres. It is known that the field of education is a part of the socio-economic network. Development and improvement of marketing strategy of the educational service will increase the competitiveness of this field and increase the efficiency of the educational service.

According to Philip Kotler's approach, higher education marketing is the analysis, planning, implementation, and monitoring of well-defined programs designed to facilitate the free exchange of value in markets for targeted educational services in pursuit of a defined goal.

In the market of educational services, the seller is considered to be a person who helps in the manifestation and formation of the market offer. In this case, the seller should have certain specialized knowledge and be able to present it to consumers based on their requirements.

Analysis and results

It is better to start studying the nature of marketing of educational services from the elements that make up its content: subjects and objects of educational services. As a rule, subjects of marketing of educational services include: educational institutions, service consumers, organizations and structures that promote educational services in the market. In the case we are studying, the professional educational institution (educational institution) itself is considered as an educational institution, and its consumers can be both legal entities and natural persons. In addition, it can only be said that the ultimate consumers (object) of the marketing of the educational institution's services are mostly representatives of the older population. For this reason, adults, as the final consumers, have a significant influence on the choice of education sources, forms, place, and time. Marketing relations referred to the provision of educational services, its programs and other types of services are formed around the interests of adults who act as consumers of educational courses.

From the point of view of practical marketing, the following can be included among the main tasks of educational services marketing performed by an educational institution:

- research and evaluation of the market of educational services, forecasting changes in its conjuncture;

- determining prospective directions of education, the size and types of services provided;
- assessment of the demand for training target groups and the possibilities of their satisfaction;

- development of pricing policy and strategy;

- determining communication policy, promotion channels, sales methods;

- implementation of services in the process of using educational services.

When organizing the marketing of educational services, it is necessary to take into account that educational services have their own aspects. The same thing distinguishes it from other goods/products that the customer can see, feel and evaluate the quality of other products while buying. Therefore, the purchase of educational services by a potential consumer is always associated with great risk. Officially, the consumer of any educational product, when signing up for a training course, has absolutely no idea what they are going to offer him. For this reason, when many listeners decide to participate in any training, they usually rely on the advice of people they know who have participated in the training course offered on the market before and achieved positive results.

In order to clearly imagine the uniqueness of educational services, it is necessary to consider the special and important aspects of teaching as a type of service.

For example, let's take a look at some of the main specific aspects of the activity of an educational institution that must be taken into account when organizing a marketing service.

First: Educational service is distinguished by its non-emotional nature, that is, it is impossible to see, listen, feel and evaluate it in advance until you buy it and start using it.

Secondly: The processes of presentation and consumption cannot be separated from each other. It is consumed after the purchase of other goods, but it is consumed at the same time that the educational service is provided. The main feature that distinguishes the educational service is that in the process of providing it, a close relationship is formed between the service provider and the consumer.

Third: Educational courses and programs as a type of service are characterized by their instability and unsatisfactory quality, and its main indicators depend on many factors and content creators. For example, the quality of teaching in one educational course depends on the content and methodology of the teacher, the level of preparation of the teacher conducting the course, the composition and enthusiasm of the audience, and even the lesson schedule and the academic season of the year.

It is also necessary to take into account that the range of evaluation of its quality indicator is extremely private when receiving educational services. The evaluation of the quality of the training course is closely related to how a particular person accepts this or that training methodology, the knowledge and skills that this person already has, the requirements and wishes he places on the content of the training program. It can be seen that all of the above may be different for different people studying in the same course. This results can vary in different grades given by the students of the same course.

Fourth: Educational services differ by their nature, for example, they are not reserved for those who do not come to the training on time or miss it. While it is possible to use other people's notes or educational handouts, it is not possible to repeat a missed session or repeat it many times. It is also worth noting that acquired knowledge can be forgotten, lost, and outdated, which creates the need to constantly update and supplement it.

Thus, in a general way, it can be said that educational service is offered by one party (educational center) to another party (student) in order to achieve quantitative and qualitative changes in the level of knowledge, skills, professional and personal competence, a type of activity that cannot be understood through emotions is envisaged. The provision of educational services is closely related to the provision of services to students, the quality of educational process management, and the chosen marketing strategy. The educational services offered by the

educational institution ultimately form the attentive attitude of consumers towards it and have a direct impact on the increase in profit.

In the organization of marketing activities of an educational institution, the educational service itself is inseparable from the teaching object of education, the so-called mentor-teacher. Professional knowledge, the use of special methods of teaching adults, the ability to attract an audience, and establish trusting relationships with listeners have a great impact on the educational outcome. Therefore, the selection and training of a teacher or other person who organizes the training process is often more important than even well-prepared programs and training materials. Mistakes made in working with the teacher can cause serious problems in the activity of the Centers (dissatisfaction of students, inability to achieve the planned result, refusal of some students to participate in classes, etc.).

Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the analysis of the received data, recommendations for further development and improvement of the marketing activity of the HEI were developed.

One of the main issues of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities is to determine the place and role of the marketing department in the organizational structure of the higher education institution, including the list of the directions of activities of its interaction with other structural units, their completeness and complexity.

In accordance with this, we evaluate the effectiveness of organizing marketing activities with the sum of the following criteria:

1. The implementation of professional activities of the marketing department: studying competitors, researching consumers, managing educational activities, organizing new ideas for educational services and programs, setting prices for services, promoting educational services and organization of effective sales, development of marketing strategy.

2. The internal environment of the marketing department: qualifications and professionalism of the employees of the marketing department, the structure of marketing expenses, methods of financing the marketing department.

An objective assessment of the organization of marketing management of higher education institutions allows to determine the position of the marketing department and the level of its business activity.

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